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ANALYZING THE PROSPECTS OF UZBEKISTAN'S NATURAL GAS AND SOLAR ENERGY RESOURCES

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Abstract. Uzbekistan, a pivotal nation on the Silk Road Economic Belt, boasts significant natural gas reserves and burgeoning solar energy potential. With 1.8 trillion cubic meters of proven natural gas, Uzbekistan is a top global miner and exporter, particularly through the China-Central Asia Gas Pipeline. The country's uranium reserves rank ninth worldwide, solidifying its position as Central Asia's second-largest resource holder. With declining natural gas production, Uzbekistan is pivoting towards solar energy, leveraging its vast solar resources, equivalent to 50.9 billion tons of oil. This shift underscores the nation's efforts to diversify its energy mix and ensure long-term energy security. Uzbekistan's initiative to construct major solar power plants, including the largest in Central Asia, signals a significant step towards sustainable energy development. International cooperation, particularly with China, is crucial for technology transfer and investment in Uzbekistan's solar energy sector.

Keywords: Uzbekistan energy, natural gas resources, solar energy development, sustainable energy transition..

Uzbekistan is an important energy resource country on the Silk Road Economic Belt. It has proven natural gas reserves of about 1.8 trillion cubic meters and is one of the world's top ten natural gas mining countries. Many large natural gas pipelines run through its territory, making it an important hub node of the China-Central Asia natural gas pipeline; Uzbekistan's proven uranium reserves rank ninth in the world, making it the second largest uranium resource country in Central Asia; the Kyzyl Kum Desert partly locates in Uzbekistan, its solar energy resources are particularly rich, with reserves equivalent to 50.9 billion tons of oil, 10 times that of Central Asia's oil resources, Uzbekistan, therefore, is called the "Kingdom of the Sun". Both gasoline resources and solar energy resources play an important role in the construction of the Silk Road energy corridor.

1 UZBEKISTAN - NATURAL GAS PIPELINE HUB ON THE SILK ROAD ENERGY CORRIDOR

China-Central Asia Oil and Gas Pipeline

The China-Central Asia Gas Pipeline passes through Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan.¹ The pipeline network includes four pipelines, A, B, C and D. A and B are double lines in parallel. The pipeline is 3,298 kilometers long in Central Asia, 525 kilometers in Uzbekistan, 2,773 kilometers in Kazakhstan, and 8,000 kilometers in China, with a total length of more than 11,000 kilometers, the longest pipeline in the world. The China-Central Asia natural gas pipeline is implemented in two phases: the first phase starts on the Uzbek side of the Turkmenistan-Uzbekistan border and connects with the planned export natural gas pipeline in Turkmenistan, receiving 30 billion cubic meters of natural gas from Turkmenistan every year; it joins with the second phase Central Asia-Central Gas Pipeline², which starts in Kazakhstan, in Chimkent, Kazakhstan, receiving 10 billion cubic meters of natural gas from Kazakhstan every year, and then goes northwest to finally reach Horgos, a border port in western China. Uzbekistan is at the hub of the China-Central Asia oil and gas pipeline.³

The China-Natural Gas Pipeline is of great significance to the Silk Road and China's economic construction. After entering China, it is connected to China's West-East Gas Pipeline. Its gas supply covers 25 provinces, autonomous regions, or municipalities in China, and reaches the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, supporting the economic development of the regions it passes through, facilitating the lives of more than 500 million people, and bringing huge economic benefits and environmental improvement benefits to these regions. Calculated based on the principle that 100 billion cubic meters of natural gas is equivalent to 133 million tons of coal, the use of 294.6 billion cubic meters of natural gas is equivalent to saving 391.8 million tons of coal, reducing carbon dioxide emissions by 142 million tons and sulfur dioxide emissions by 2.2 million tons; during the operation period, it can generate a total of US\$3.1 billion in tax revenue for the transit countries, realize US\$5.4 billion in shareholder dividends, and create tens of thousands of job opportunities [1].

The huge geo-economic significance of the China-Central Asia Energy Corridor

The total length of the China-Central Asia Energy Corridor exceeds 11,000 kilometers. Together with the China-Kazakhstan oil pipeline with an oil transportation capacity of 20 million tons/year, it constitutes a huge supply and demand pattern of oil and gas resources in Asia. The oil and gas resource pattern is no longer a single Gulf type [1].⁴

The destination of Central Asian oil and gas resources was originally westward, mainly transported by the Caspian Sea Oil Pipeline (CPC). The China-Kazakhstan oil and gas resource cooperation opened up the eastward transportation route of Central Asian oil and gas resources as well as the Silk Road oil and gas corridor. During this period, Russia emerged as a major oil and gas resource country. On the one hand, it was squeezed by NATO's eastward expansion, and its traditional westward oil and gas export channels were obstructed; on the other hand, it was

¹ Its D line also passes through Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, covering the entire Central Asian region passed by the ancient Silk Road. It is a veritable Silk Road energy corridor.

² The Beineu compressor station.

³ At present, Lines A, B and C have been put into operation, and Line D is under construction. This line enters China from southern Xinjiang and ends at the terminal in Wuqia, Xinjiang. With its 1,000 kilometers long and a designed annual gas transmission capacity of 30 billion cubic meters, the overall gas transmission capacity of the China-Central Asia Natural Gas Pipeline will reach 85 billion cubic meters. The China-Central Asia Natural Gas Pipeline can meet more than 20% of China's domestic natural gas demand. Since the Central Asia Natural Gas Pipeline was put into operation in December 2009 until December 31, 2019, a total of 294.6 billion cubic meters of gas has been delivered.

⁴ By the end of 2020, Central Asia will be able to deliver 90 million tons of oil and gas to China annually.

attracted by the rise of an emerging oil and gas demand center in the East, and sought new ways to export oil and gas to the East, thus opening up the eastward oil and gas channel in the China-Russia cooperation. The China-Central Asia oil and gas corridor meets the China-Russia oil and gas corridor, building an inland oil and gas resource supply and demand framework that mainly meets China's oil and gas needs. This is a unique initiative. Previously, China's oil shortage depended on the supply of the Persian Gulf, Africa, and South America countries. The transportation of oil and gas across the ocean was not only costly, but also had to bear the risk of maritime safety. Now such resources can be partially obtained from the inland of Asia, which not only greatly reduces the transportation cost, but also improves the safety. With the consolidation and extension of this supply and demand pattern, the share of oil shortage from Asia inland supply will expand, and its economic and political benefits will be further improved. This strengthening and expansion will contribute to form a new inland oil and gas supply and demand pattern that is different from the traditional Gulf-type, which is actually controlled by the US oil and gas consortium. There is no doubt that the new oil and gas supply and demand pattern will have an impact on the Gulf-type and affect the existing geo-economic and geopolitical pattern. Here, the Russian factor plays an important role, which is determined by its resource backing and geo-economic status.

The China-Central Asia natural gas pipeline mainly supplies northwest, central, east and south China (including Hong Kong and Macao); the China-Russia East Line natural gas pipeline mainly supplies Northeast China and North China. The two lines are compatible and the gas supply almost covers the whole country, building an inland natural gas supply and demand framework. China's annual natural gas demand is about 400 billion cubic meters, and the self-sufficiency is 40%, that is, 160 billion cubic meters need to be imported. The west and east ends receive a total of 123 billion (850+380) cubic meters of natural gas each year, that is, the China-Central Asia natural gas pipeline and the China-Russia East Line natural gas pipeline together can fill 76.88% of China's natural gas import demand, which is enough to illustrate the significant role of the inland energy supply and demand pattern in China's oil and gas resource demand.

2 THE DECLINE OF NATURAL GAS PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE RISE OF ITS SOLAR ENERGY DEVELOPMENT

The current proven recoverable oil reserves in Central Asia are 4.2682 billion tons, with an annual oil production of 90.7856 million tons. It can be inferred that at the current mining rate, it can be mined for 47 years. Because there is a recovery rate problem in oil mining, it is impossible to take out all the mineral resources underground⁵. Under normal circumstances, it is good to be able to extract 50%. Therefore, how much underground reserves can be taken out needs to be multiplied by a recovery factor, such as 0.5, so 47 years becomes about 24 years. It should also be considered here that the demand for oil is growing, and the mining volume will increase accordingly. The annual oil mining volume in Central Asia is now about 90 million tons. Some

⁵ Take oil for example, because it is stored underground in a viscous form, generally speaking, in the primary oil recovery stage using the natural energy of the formation, usually only 8% to 15% of the underground crude oil can be recovered; in the secondary oil recovery stage using artificial supplementation of formation energy (such as water injection, gas injection, etc.), the recovery rate of underground crude oil is 25% to 45%; in the tertiary oil recovery stage, the final recovery rate can reach 45% to 70%, which can only be achieved through special process technology means that are more complex than water injection and gas injection, and the investment itself is very large, and the cost will be greatly increased.

people predict that it will increase to 120 million tons in recent years and reach 150 million tons before 2020. The remaining volume will not be mined for 24 years. There are also predicted reserves (geological reserves) of 11 billion tons, which can be exploited for about twice as long, but the predicted reserves may not all be realized. The United Nations Development Program has a comprehensive assessment that the peak of oil and gas production in Central Asia will come between 2025 and 2030 [2] and thereafter it will face an oil and gas resource crisis, which is earlier than most people think.

According to the Uzbek Economic Research Center, after 2020, Uzbekistan's oil shortage will continue to grow, and the country's energy security will be threatened by 2030. The shortage will reach 4.5 million tons of oil equivalent, and the growth momentum of natural gas production will stop. With the growth of domestic consumption, natural gas exports will be compressed and will be reduced by 10 billion cubic meters in 2030 compared with 2020. After 2030, in order to ensure national energy stability, 12 million to 13 million tons of oil equivalent of replacement energy will be needed, which is 21% of the current national energy balance sheet. Uzbekistan, a major natural gas country in Central Asia, has felt that the peak of natural gas production is about to pass, and the energy threat is just around the corner. It is not difficult to see that the foresighted scholars in the Central Asian have already felt the trend that "the hydrocarbon economy era is coming to an end."

In fact, Uzbekistan has already imported 9 million cubic meters of natural gas from Russia in October 2024, and it is expected to import 5.6 billion cubic meters of natural gas within two years. Uzbekistan's solar energy is estimated at 50.9 billion tons of oil equivalent, and it plans to reduce the use of hydrocarbon energy in energy production by 50% by 2050.

Broad prospects for the development of solar energy resources in Uzbekistan [3]

Since traditional energy sources such as oil and natural gas are exhaustible and cause environmental pollution, the development and utilization of new energy sources is not only a replacement for traditional energy sources, but also a protection of the ecological environment and a support for the sustainable development of the social economy. The energy crisis means that traditional energy sources will be exhausted one day, which is precisely an opportunity to new energy sources and the development of solar energy in Uzbekistan. The solar energy potential of 50.9 billion tons of oil equivalent will be a vast world for solar energy development, and its prospect significance may exceed that of the China-Central Asia natural gas pipeline.

Central Asia has considerable solar energy potential. The total area of the Karakum, Kyzylkum, Sareyesik-Atlaikum, Moinkum and other deserts is 830,000 square kilometers, providing a vast place for desert industry-solar energy utilization in Central Asia. Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan each have two of the largest deserts, making them countries with unique solar energy resources. The daytime sunshine lasts up to 16 hours in July, and 1 square meter of light radiation can generate 800 megawatts of electricity. There are up to 300 daytime days a year, and the solar radiation time is up to 2500-3000 hours. In the southwestern part of the country, between the Kashkadarya and Sursondarya districts, the solar energy intensity reaches 4.9-5.1 kWh/m² per day.

According to relevant data, the solar energy reserves in Uzbekistan alone are equivalent to 50.9 billion tons of oil, which is 10 times the oil resources in Central Asia. Therefore, Uzbekistan is called the "Land of the Sun". The Uzbek government plans to significantly expand the development and application of solar energy in the shortest possible time and has allocated 253 hectares of land for the construction of solar power stations [4]. The project has been approved to build a 100-megawatt solar power station in the Pasterdalgom area of Samarkand, the largest in

Central Asia. The completion of this project will improve the power supply conditions of residents in Pasterdalgom, Nurabat, Katakurgan and Narpai. In recent years, Uzbekistan will build several large solar power plants, set up photovoltaic panel production lines, build energy-saving houses, and establish solar power generation experimental equipment for remote mountain schools. With Uzbekistan's existing technology, the electricity that can be obtained from solar energy is equivalent to 179 million tons of oil, which is more than twice the country's current oil production.

In early April 2015, when a 130-kilowatt solar power station in Namangan Province, Uzbekistan, was put into operation, Uzbek scholar Alexander Kosachev published an article, saying that this was "Uzbekistan's first step towards the sun"[5].

Chinese factors in the development of solar energy resources in Uzbekistan

In 2014, Uzbekistan cooperated with Chinese enterprises to build a 100-megawatt photovoltaic panel production line in the Navoi Free Industrial Economic Zone and an enterprise with an annual output of 50,000 solar collectors in the Jizzakh Special Industrial Zone. In 2009, Uzbekistan established a renewable energy technology park and opened up the solar energy investment market. In terms of cooperation, it chose the method of importing photovoltaic cells, jointly building photovoltaic power stations, and establishing photovoltaic cell production bases in Central Asia.

China's solar photovoltaic industry technology is at the world's leading level, and technical exchanges with Central Asian new energy development have started for many years. The International Cooperation Department of the Ministry of Science and Technology and the Xinjiang Central Asian Science and Technology Economic Information Center have jointly held 5 "Central Asian Solar Energy Development and Utilization Technology International Training Courses" in Xinjiang, trained more than 100 professional and technical personnel from five Central Asian countries and Russia. During the study period, in addition to listening to expert lectures in the classroom, the trainees also conducted on-site inspections, which promoted the understanding of the technical level of China's solar energy industry and promoted the scientific and technological cooperation between China and Central Asia in the field of solar energy development. Adilkhozhaev Shukhrat, acting director of the Scientific Innovation Center under the Uzbek State Environmental Protection Committee, said that China is in a world-leading position in the development and utilization of some new energy sources, especially in the field of solar energy. He hopes that the trainees will enhance mutual understanding and find ways for cooperation between two countries during the course [6]. Most of the trainees have become technical backbones of local solar energy development after returning to their country, promoting cooperation between their country and Xinjiang in the development of solar energy resources. Adilkhozhaev Shukhrat said that Uzbekistan will build large-scale solar power plants, energy-saving houses, and solar power stations for remote mountainous areas in recent years, as well as set up photovoltaic cell production lines, hoping to carry out exchanges and cooperation with China [7]. In 2014, Uzbekistan will cooperate with Chinese companies to build a 100-megawatt photovoltaic panel production line in the Navoi Free Industrial Economic Zone and a solar collector production enterprise with an annual output of 50,000 units in the Jike Special Industrial Zone.

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